

Theoretical Foundations Of Modeling Military Exercises

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Abstract: *This article describes the theoretical bases of pedagogical modeling, its essence and efficiency. Modeling, being one of the methods of the scientific study, is broadly used in pedagogy. The Method of modeling is an integrative, he allows to unite empirical and theoretical in pedagogical study i.e. combine in the course of studies of the pedagogical object experiment with building logical design and scientific abstraction.*

Keywords — modeling, theory, pedagogue, method, formation, projecting, planning.

INTRODUCTION.

One of the priority directions for the development of society is “the formation of a perfect system of personnel training based on the rich intellectual heritage of the people and universal human values, the achievements of modern culture, economics, science, engineering and technology.”

The great Abu Raykhon Beruni said: “Science must serve the people and the progress of society.” Science, according to Beruni, arises from the need to satisfy the vital needs of people. We must not allow a vacuum or emptiness to appear in politics, in public life, and in science.

There is no learning without knowledge, education and development. Neglect of any of these aspects leads to tangible losses: the absence of the educational (cognitive) aspect does not develop motivation (through the cognitive aspect); the absence of a developmental aspect has a detrimental effect on mastering skills; the exclusion of targeted education does not contribute to the formation of personality, although it is known that society needs not just an expert on something, not just a person who knows how to communicate, but a moral person who has the skills and abilities to communicate both in everyday life and in professional activities. Consequently, the learning process includes not only an educational goal, but also pedagogical and psychological content. And all this should be included in the education system.

“A good textbook,” as K.D. Ushinsky rightly asserted, “is the foundation of a good education”³. In order to create such a foundation, it is necessary to determine the leading principled approaches to the content, procedural and educational aspects of the textbook, as well as to think through the “infrastructure” of textbooks of the 3rd millennium. In other words, to develop the necessary components of an educational and methodological complex in which the textbook, on the one hand, acts as one of the links in the linguodidactic system as a whole, and on the other, as a central component that regulates and guides the entire learning process⁴.

To solve this problem, it is necessary to study the theoretical foundations of pedagogical modeling, mastery of modeling techniques with the general method of scientific knowledge, and the need to solve psychological and pedagogical problems. When students build various models of

the phenomena being studied, modeling acts both as a teaching tool and as a way to generalize educational material, as well as present it in a condensed form. In addition, modeling educational material is widely used for its logical ordering, constructing semantic schemes, presenting educational information in a visual form and relying on figurative associations using mnemonic rules.

In pedagogical science, the modeling method is substantiated in the works of M.Kh.Tokhtakhodjaev, K.Hoshimov, Zh.Hasanboev, H.Sariboev, V.G.Afanasyev, V.A.Venikov, I.B.Novik, V.A.Shtoff, etc. Let us use the most complete, in our opinion, definition of modeling given by G.V. Sukhodolsky, who interprets it “as the process of creating a hierarchy of models in which some really existing system is modeled in various aspects and by various means.” The main concept of the modeling method is the model.

A model is an artificially created object in the form of a diagram, physical structures, symbolic forms or formulas, which, being similar to the object (or phenomenon) under study, displays and reproduces in a simpler and more generalized form the structure, properties, interconnections and relationships between the elements of this object¹.

In this case, as a rule, direct study of an object is associated with some difficulties, for example, of a financial or technical nature. It is customary to conventionally divide models into three types: physical (having a nature similar to the original); material-mathematical (their physical nature differs from the prototype, but a mathematical description of the behavior of the original is possible); logical-semiotic (constructed from special signs, symbols and structural diagrams).

There are no hard boundaries between these types of models. Pedagogical models are mainly included in the second and third groups of listed types.

The practical value of a model in any pedagogical research is mainly determined by its adequacy to the studied aspects of the object, as well as by how correctly the basic principles of modeling are taken into account at the stages of constructing the model - clarity, certainty, objectivity, which largely determine both the capabilities and type of the model, and its functions in educational research.

The effectiveness of modeling depends on the initial theories and hypotheses that indicate the limits of

simplifications permissible in modeling. Therefore, the most important question is: How to solve the problem of model adequacy? All researchers using modeling apparatus attach special importance to this aspect. There is an important methodological point in this regard.

The Austrian logician Kurt Gödel proved two famous theorems on the incompleteness and consistency of formal systems². The first asserts that in logical-mathematical systems it is fundamentally impossible to formalize the entire content, i.e. any system of axioms is incomplete. The second talks about the impossibility of proving the consistency of a formal system by means of this system itself.

Gödel's theorems have also received a general scientific interpretation, according to which for the deductive construction of a model that accurately describes the "behavior" of a system of any nature, there is no complete and finite set of information about it. To describe the effectiveness of modeling, a special concept was introduced into pedagogy - pedagogical validity, which is close to reliability and adequacy, but not identical to them. Pedagogical modeling has a "partner term" that often accompanies it in scientific texts – design.

In some publications, these terms are used as comparable and substitute for each other, i.e. they are synonymous, where appropriate. The word "project" has several meanings, and almost all of them are related to pedagogy. First, the draft is a preliminary (tentative) text of a document. Secondly, the project is understood as a certain action, a set of activities united by one programme or in an organisational form of purposeful activity.

In this sense, the term "project as a form of research activity of students" is used in training. And the third meaning of the project is the activity of creating (developing, planning, constructing) any system, object or model. V.E. Rodionov, when analysing the essence of design, highlights, first of all, its iterative nature, when an object is repeatedly modelled and appropriate decisions are made in order to approach a satisfactory solution.

Based on the conducted scientific analysis, when comparing the concepts of "design" and "modeling", he writes: "Design makes extensive use of modeling as a means of representing and transforming an object that does not yet exist in reality. This distinguishes modeling in design from modeling in theory, where a model is a means to isolate an essential aspect from a real object, truncate the latter for the convenience of subsequent logical analysis.

Modeling in design allows us to operate with objects about which we do not have complete knowledge." Thus, design is aimed at creating models of planned (future) processes and phenomena, in contrast to modeling, which can extend to past experience in order to understand it more deeply.

The components of the project activity can be specific models or modules (functional nodes that combine a set of elements, for example, an educational system). A person's project activity is conditioned by his ability to build in his

mind, to come up with ideal models that only partially reflect reality, and partially reflect the subjective world of a person, his values and goals

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